

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Pannonian Region (Hungary)

PROBLEM

What are the most effective agroecological strategies for weed management in perennial crops in the Pannonian Region?

STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS

Mowing is the most used weed control technique for perennial crops in the Pannonian Region. They also employ inert and living mulches, along with perennial ground cover plants. These methods are favoured because they easily integrate into conventional farming and require minimal attention, providing direct benefits to farmers. Many stakeholders are familiar with seasonal cover crops, grazing, weeding, and ploughing, but most do not actively use these methods. Participants view mixed cropping, mulching, and cover crops as effective weed management strategies. However, the high cost of mulching limits its adoption. Additionally, stakeholders highlighted the need for soil-friendly mechanical weeding practices and improvements in machine design. The challenge of replacing herbicides is also significant, with calls for developing alternative chemicals that are less harmful to plants and ecosystems.

Figure 1: Perennial intercropping system in Fertőd (Source: Andrea Vityi)

RECOMMENDATION

Establish an experimental design with ecosystem-friendly practices usable in organic production such as mixed cropping (perennial crops in agroforestry intercropping) combined with inter-row weeding and use of effective bio substances that trigger herbicides.

KEYWORDS

agroforestry, weed, agroecological, bioherbicide, perennial

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